

MAGNETO-CHEMICAL STUDIES IN VALENCY AND MOLECULAR CONSTITUTION. PART II. MAGNETIC MOMENT AND MOLECULAR CONFIGURATION OF SOME TRIPLE NITRITES AND METALLIC CYANIDES CONTAINING ELEMENTS OF THE FIRST TRANSITIONAL SERIES

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A number of triple nitrites containing bivalent Co, Ni, Cu and Fe as the central atom and a double nitrite of bivalent nickel have been magneto-chemically examined. From a consideration of their magnetic moment values it has been concluded that almost all of them belong to the penetration type of co-ordination complexes with fairly strong co-valent bonds.

Magnetic susceptibilities of both hydrated and anhydrous nickel cyanides, prepared from extremely pure ingredients, have also been measured. The observed moment values have been found to agree with those given by some of the previous workers. Following Pauling an explanation has been advanced for the values thus obtained which are much lower than that of the nickelous ion in its simple salts, and a configuration for the anhydrous cyanide has been suggested on the basis of planar d_{sp^2} bonds together with a few ionic bonds in the form of polymerised molecules.

Cobaltous cyanide, both in the hydrated and anhydrous state, have also been found to behave magnetically like the nickel cyanide, and in the anhydrous state consists like the latter of polymerised molecules with the cobaltous atom in both planar d_{sp^2} bonds and ionic bonds.

A number of triple nitrites containing bivalent iron, cobalt, nickel and copper has long been described in the literature. The strong and striking colour of these seems to suggest that they are true penetration complexes and are not mere molecular compounds or triple salts. Their instability, due to more or less rapid hydrolysis in water, obviously precludes their study by the usual physico-chemical methods generally applicable to solutions. Under the circumstances, the magnetic method of investigation at once suggests itself as a very convenient and ready means of determining the nature of the chemical bond between the transitional metal atom and the nitrito groups, and thus deciding the configuration of the molecule as a whole. The present work was undertaken with this end in view.

Magnetic measurements have also been made on the hydrated and anhydrous cyanides of bivalent nickel and cobalt; and a discussion of the results has led to an insight into their molecular configuration and the nature of the metal-cyanogen bond.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Materials.

1. *Potassium Calcium Cobalto-nitrite.*—A solution of 2.4 g. of nickel-free cobalt chloride (Scherring-Kahlbaum) dissolved in the least amount of cold water was added to that of calcium chloride, prepared from 3 g. of calcium carbonate (guaranteed reagent, Scherring-Kahlbaum), and the mixture was thoroughly cooled. A neutral solution of potassium nitrite was prepared by dissolving 14 g. of the pure salt (Scherring-Kahlbaum) in 25 c.c. of cold water and carefully neutralising the solution to phenolphthalein. This was cooled in ice and the two solutions were then mixed together in a beaker surrounded with ice and the mixture was vigorously stirred for 15 minutes. A dirty yellowish green product separated from the mixture. This was filtered by suction in a Buchner funnel and was

washed thrice with ice-cold water, then with cold 50% dilute alcohol and finally with absolute alcohol. The product was dried in air to a constant weight (*cf.* Cuttica and Paoletti, *Gazzetta*, 1922, 52, 276). {Found : Co, 13.07, 12.98 ; Ca, 7.92, 7.90 ; K, 18.43, 18.70 ; NO₂, 60.90, 60.81. K₂Ca[Co(NO₂)₆] requires Co, 13.03 ; Ca, 8.83 ; K, 17.22 ; NO₂, 60.90 per cent}.

The results show that the proportion of K and Ca does not agree with the theoretical value as given by Cuttica and Paoletti (*loc. cit.*). Several samples were prepared by varying the proportion between the constituents. But all attempts to prepare the compound of the given composition led always to variable values for K and Ca, though the sum of their equivalent proportions remained unchanged, being equal to 4 in all cases, as demanded by the principle of electrical neutrality for the molecule as a whole. Hence, an isomorphous replacement obviously occurs under all circumstances between K⁺ and Ca⁺⁺ ions which do not differ considerably either in their size or mass.

2. *Potassium Lead Cobalto-nitrite*.—Its preparation resembles that of the previously described calcium salt, calcium chloride being replaced by lead nitrate. The substance formed a dark black, micro-crystalline precipitate. This was dried in a vacuum desiccator to a constant weight (Cuttica and Paoletti, *loc. cit.*). {Found : Co, 9.49, 9.50 ; Pb, 33.43, 33.41 ; K, 12.70, 12.71 ; NO₂, 44.30, 44.40. K₂Pb[Co(NO₂)₆] requires Co, 9.52 ; Pb, 33.40 ; K, 12.60 ; NO₂, 44.50 per cent}.

3. *Potassium calcium nickelo-nitrite* was prepared in the same way as the corresponding cobalt salt described above, cobalt-free nickel nitrate replacing the cobalt nitrate. The substance, which separated as a light yellow micro-crystalline precipitate, was washed with ice-cold water, 30% acetone solution and with pure acetone in succession. It was dried in air (*cf.* Erdmann, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1864, 3, 161 ; Mousseron and Carriteau, *J. Pharm. Chem.*, 1932, 16, 282). {Found : Ca, 7.90 ; K, 15.51 ; Ni, 11.60 ; NO₂, 54.53. K₂Ca[Ni(NO₂)₆] requires Ca, 7.91 ; K, 15.43 ; Ni, 11.58 ; NO₂, 54.44 per cent}.

4. *Potassium nickelo-nitrite* was prepared from cobalt-free nickel nitrate and a neutral solution of potassium nitrite in a manner similar to that adopted for the preparation of the triple salt described above. The orange-red precipitate was washed successively with small quantity of ice-cold water, 30% cold acetone and finally with pure acetone. The substance was dried in air to a constant weight (*cf.* Erdmann and also Mousseron and Carriteau, *loc. cit.*). {Found : K, 31.83 ; Ni, 11.97 ; NO₂, 56.10. K₄[Ni(NO₂)₆] requires K, 31.85 ; Ni, 11.95 ; NO₂, 56.22 per cent}.

5. *Potassium Calcium Cupri-nitrite*.—Chemically pure recrystallised copper chloride (8.5 g.) was dissolved in 25 c.c. of cold aqueous solution of 15 g. pure sodium nitrite. There was a slight evolution of heat and of some N₂O₃ with the precipitation of a little basic copper salt. The solution was filtered and treated with a neutral solution (30 c.c.) of calcium chloride prepared from 5 g. of calcium carbonate (Scherring-Kahlbaum, guaranteed reagent), which also contained 20 g. of pure sodium nitrite and 7.4 g. of pure potassium chloride (Merck). The solutions were cooled to 5° before mixing by means of a freezing mixture. On stirring for about ten minutes a crystalline green precipitate separated out and some nitrous fumes were evolved. After cooling thoroughly it was filtered at the pump to remove most of the mother-liquor. The substance was then made into a paste with 85% alcohol, and allowed to settle. The alcohol was then poured out and

the substance was then stirred with a little acetone and transferred to the filter. It was afterwards washed with absolute alcohol and dried to a constant weight in a vacuum desiccator (*cf.* Przibylla, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1897, 15, 419). {Found : Cu, 14.03 ; Ca, 8.75 ; K, 17.0 ; NO₂, 59.44. K₂Ca[Cu(NO₂)₆] requires Cu, 13.90 ; Ca, 8.72 ; K, 17.04 ; NO₂, 60.32 per cent}.

6. *Ammonium Lead Cupri-nitrite*.—Copper nitrate (4.8 g.) prepared from electrolytic copper was dissolved in 30 c.c. of a solution containing 6.6 g. of chemically pure lead nitrate (Kahlbaum) in it. The mixture was made neutral to litmus. 3.2 G. of chemically pure ammonium nitrite (Merck) and 16.5 g. of pure sodium nitrite were dissolved in 30 c.c. of water and this solution was also made neutral to litmus. The solutions were cooled to 8° and filtered. They were then mixed together in a beaker cooled in ice and the mixture was stirred for about 15 minutes. On standing, a black crystalline salt settled down. It was filtered at the pump and washed successively with small quantities of ice-cold water, 30% acetone solution and finally with pure acetone. The product was dried in a vacuum desiccator to a constant weight (Przibylla, *loc. cit.*). {Found : Cu, 11.03 ; Pb, 35.50 ; NH₄, 6.23 ; NO₂, 47.0. (NH₄)₂Pb[Cu(NO₂)₆] requires Cu, 10.90 ; Pb, 35.54 ; NH₄, 6.20 ; NO₂, 47.39 per cent}.

7. *Potassium Lead Ferro-nitrite*.—The method described by Przibylla (*loc. cit.*) was found to give impure product contaminated with ferric hydroxide, resulting presumably from hydrolytic decomposition and oxidation of ferrous to ferric iron by the nitrous fumes evolved from the mixture. To avoid these the following procedure was adopted.

The preparation was made at a low temperature in a current of carbon dioxide in Kapsenberg's filtering apparatus as shown in the figure below. All water used in this preparation was previously boiled and cooled.

5.56 G. of doubly recrystallised (in presence of electrolytic iron and a little dilute sulphuric acid) FeSO₄·7H₂O (A.R. quality) and 14 g. of chemically pure lead nitrate (Kahlbaum) were made into a paste with 25 c.c. cold 60% absolute alcohol in a glass mortar. The solution containing ferrous and lead nitrate was filtered into a stoppered bottle and cooled in ice. Another solution was prepared by dissolving 4 g. of pure potassium nitrate (Merck) and 14 g. of sodium nitrite in the least quantity of water. The solution was made neutral to phenolphthalein, filtered into a stoppered bottle and cooled in ice. Now the lid A (*vide* Fig. 1) was fitted air-tight with grease to the filtering funnel B and held tightly by means of four clips ; the air inside was removed by allowing a stream of pure and dry carbon dioxide to enter through T₂ and escape by T₃, the stop-cocks T₁ and T₄ being closed. The apparatus was cooled by surrounding it with a piece of flannel soaked in a freezing mixture, and ice-cold water was allowed to drop continuously upon the flannel. Now the two solutions, prepared as above, were introduced

into the apparatus through the small funnel F and the stop-cock T₁ was at once closed.

The mixture was left for about fifteen minutes with occasional shaking when the reaction took place in the vessel B. It was then allowed to settle for about 10 minutes. An orange-yellow precipitate separated out. Now the stop-cock T_4 was opened and T_2 closed. The passage of carbon dioxide was continued throughout the entire operation. The side-tube C of the filtering flask was then connected to the pump and the liquid was filtered off rapidly. The precipitate was then washed successively twice with small quantity of ice-cold water, thrice with 30% cold acetone and then with absolute alcohol. Finally it was washed several times with anhydrous ether. The wash liquids were introduced through F by opening T_1 . The current of CO_2 was drawn through it for another 15 minutes and then the substance was taken out and dried for 20 minutes in a vacuum desiccator. The product was at once analysed and its susceptibility determined. {Found : Fe, 9.25, 9.31 ; Pb, 33.51, 33.32 ; K, 12.75 ; NO_2 , 44.55. $\text{K}_2\text{Pb}[\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$ requires Fe, 9.08 ; Pb, 33.55 ; K, 12.64 ; NO_2 , 44.73 per cent.}

8 (a). *Cobaltous Cyanide (hydrated)*.—5 G. of nickel-free, chemically pure, cobalt chloride (Scherring-Kahlbaum) were dissolved in 250 c.c. water ; a dilute solution of 2 g. chemically pure potassium cyanide (Merck) was added dropwise to the above solution and the mixture thoroughly stirred. Cobaltous cyanide was precipitated as an amorphous mass. The precipitate was allowed to settle on the water-bath and washed several times by decantation until the supernatant liquid was free from chloride. The substance was separated from the mother-liquor and the wash liquid by centrifuging. The product was finally washed with absolute alcohol. It was dried in air at about 30° to a constant weight (cf. Biltz and co-workers, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1928, 170, 164). {Found : N, 18.10 ; Co, 37.70. $\text{Co}(\text{CN})_2, 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 17.96 ; Co, 37.82 per cent.}

(b) *Anhydrous Cobaltous Cyanide*.—The hydrated cobaltous cyanide (*vide supra*) was weighed into a specially designed dehydration tube shown in the figure below.

FIG. 2.

The tube T_1 , one end of which is sealed, can be freely glided in or out of the neck of the small bulb tube B and is kept in position by means of a rubber tube R_1 . There is a small hole at h in T_1 . When T_1 is drawn out so that h reaches A, beyond the end of the neck of B, the hole is closed, and the connection between the bulb tube and the outside air is cut off (II-position). When h is in the position I, the bulb is open to the air. The end

of the side tube T_2 is ground and fits tightly into the mouth of the susceptibility tube. T_2 can be closed by means of a small glass rod g fitting tightly in the rubber tube R_2 . The dehydration tube containing the substance was placed in the cavity of an aluminium block fitted with a thermometer and heated by a micro-burner at the base. The air inside the bulb tube was expelled by a current of dry nitrogen gas from a cylinder. The gas entered through the hole of the sliding tube pushed inside as in position I and escaped through the side-tube. The substance was heated at $260\text{--}280^\circ$ for several hours, the stream of nitrogen being maintained throughout the heating until the weight became constant. The nitrogen gas was dried by passing through conc. H_2SO_4 before it entered

the tube and escaped through T_2 connected with a wash-bottle containing conc. H_2SO_4 . Before cutting off the nitrogen stream, T_1 was pulled out to close the hole and T_2 closed by a rubber tube and a small glass rod as already described. The heating was repeated till all water was removed, which was determined by weighing the apparatus (*cf.* Biltz and co-workers, *loc. cit.*). {Found: Co, 53.11. $Co(CN)_2$ requires Co, 53.15 per cent. Loss of H_2O , 29.10; calc., 28.85 per cent}.

9. (a) *Nickel Cyanide Trihydrate*.—6 G. of cobalt-free nickel sulphate heptahydrate (Scherring-Kahlbaum) were dissolved in 300 c.c. water and a dilute solution of Merck's chemically pure potassium cyanide (2.5 g.) was added to it drop by drop with constant stirring. Nickel cyanide separated in the form of a green amorphous precipitate. The precipitate was allowed to settle on the water-bath and washed repeatedly by decantation with hot water until the supernatant liquid was free from Ni. The substance was then separated from the mother-liquor by centrifuging. It was then stirred twice with absolute alcohol which was afterwards removed in the same manner. The product was dried in air to a constant weight (*cf.* Hofmann and Hochtlen, *Ber.*, 1903, 38, 1149). {Found: N, 16.95; Ni, 35.60. $Ni(CN)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$ requires N, 17.0; Ni, 35.63 per cent}.

(b) *Nickel cyanide dihydrate* was prepared according to the method described by Hofmann and Hochtlen (*loc. cit.*). Cobalt-free nickel sulphate heptahydrate (5 g., Scherring-Kahlbaum) was dissolved in 20 c.c. water and added to a solution of 2.5 g. of chemically pure potassium cyanide (Merck) in 10 c.c. water. The precipitate of nickel cyanide was then dissolved by adding to the mixture 20 c.c. of liquor ammonia. After allowing the solution to stand for 15 minutes in ice, it was filtered through glass wool. The clear blue solution was kept aside for several days when with the gradual loss of ammonia layers of crystalline flakes separated from the solution. The crystals were filtered and washed free from nickel. They were finally washed with absolute alcohol and dried to a constant weight in air. {Found: N, 19.14; Ni, 40.10. $Ni(CN)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ requires N, 19.0; Ni, 40.01 per cent}.

(c) *Anhydrous Nickel Cyanide*.—The trihydrate, $Ni(CN)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$, was heated in the dehydration tube (*vide* the preparation of anhydrous cobaltous cyanide) at 190-200° to a constant weight (*cf.* Biltz and co-workers, *loc. cit.*; Vournasos, *Compt. rend.*, 1919, 168, 889). {Found: Ni, 53.10. $Ni(CN)_2$ requires Ni, 53.03 per cent. Loss of H_2O by heat, 32.83; calc. from $Ni(CN)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$, 32.78 per cent}.

Measurement of Magnetic Susceptibilities.

The susceptibility of the above described substances was measured according to Gouy's method as described in a previous paper by one of us (*cf.* Rây and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 323). The mass susceptibility, χ_g , was calculated from the formula,

$$\chi_g = \frac{2l \times m(\text{change of weight in mg.})}{m \times H^2 \times 1.019}$$

the symbols represent values as stated in previous papers ($H=10.15 \times 10^3$ gauss, $l=9$ cm.). The correction due to air displacement being negligible in the present cases has

been ignored. The molecular susceptibility, χ_m , has been corrected for atomic and ionic diamagnetism, the values and sources of which are mentioned below.

K^+	$= -14.9 \times 10^{-6}$	
CN^-	$= -13.0 \times$	Trew, <i>Trans. Faraday Soc.</i> , 1941, 37, 488.
NH_4^+	$= -13.3 \times$	
Pb^{2+}	$= -32.0 \times$	Theoretical (after Angus)
Ca^{2+}	$= -10.4 \times$	" "
Cu^{2+}	$= -12.8 \times$	" "
Fe^{2+}	$= -$	Taken to be equal to that of Zn^{2+} due to almost equality of their ionic radii. cf. Kido, <i>Sci. Report Tohoku Imp. Univ.</i> , 1932, 21, 149, 288.
Co^{2+}	$= -$	
Ni^{2+}	$= -$	
H_2O	$= -12.96 \times 10^{-6}$	
NO_2	$= -2.11 \times$	From Pascal's corrected values.

From the corrected gram atomic susceptibility for the central metal ion the value of its magnetic moment in terms of Bohr magneton was calculated from the well known relation,

$$\mu_B = 2.83 \sqrt{\chi_A} \times T$$

The results of measurement are recorded in the following table.

Substance.	Temp.	$\chi_g \times 10^6$	$\chi_m \times 10^6$	χ_A OR $\chi_m(\text{corr.})$	μ_B .
$K_2Ca[Co(NO_2)_6]$	24.3	2.97	1346	1411.6	1.83
$K_2Pb[Co(NO_2)_6]$	28	2.035	1282	1349.2	1.80
$K_2Ca[Ni(NO_2)_6] \cdot 3H_2O$	31	6.965	3530	3633.7	2.97
$K_2[Ni(NO_2)_6]$	32	6.861	3369	3453.2	2.90
$K_2Ca[Cu(NO_2)_6]$	27	2.893	1325	1390.6	1.83
$(NH_4)_2Pb[Cu(NO_2)_6]$	27	2.329	1357.5	1441.5	1.86
$K_2Pb[Fe(NO_2)_6]$	31	0.396	244.1	331.3	0.90
$Co(CN)_2 \cdot 2.5H_2O$	28	36.26	5656	5727.2	3.72
$Co(CN)_2$	29	40.35	4478	4616.8	3.30
$Ni(CN)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$	31	11.64	1917	1994.0	2.20
$Ni(CN)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	32.5	14.11	2069	2133.0	2.28
$Ni(CN)_2$	33.5	1.23	135.8	173.8	0.65

DISCUSSION

The magnetic moment for the central cobaltous atom in the case of $K_2Ca(Pb)[Co(NO_2)_6]$ has been found to be 1.83 and 1.80 Bohr respectively. A value of 1.9 μ_B for the potassium-calcium salt has been recorded by Pauling in his book, "The Nature of the Chemical Bond, 1940, p. 116." The results closely accord with the expected theoretical value for the six co-valent penetration cobaltous complexes with d^2sp^3 octahedral bonds on the

basis of Bose-Stoner's formula for one unpaired electron with quenched orbital moments. This is evident from the following scheme of electronic distribution in the complex :

This shows that the triple nitrites of dyad cobalt belong to the penetration type of octahedral complexes.

The magnetic moment of the central nickel atom in its double and triple nitrites has been found to lie between 2.90 and 2.97 Bohr. Nickel atom, in an octahedral complex of the penetration type forming d^2sp^3 bonds, must have two of its $3d$ electrons promoted to a higher level where they may remain unpaired. This should give rise to a magnetic moment, according to Bose-Stoner's formula, $\mu_n = \sqrt{4S(S+1)}$, of $\sqrt{8}$ or 2.83 Bohr magnetons, which agrees with the observed values. This holds good also for the simple Ni^{++} ion as well as for the associated tetrahedral or octahedral complexes of sp^3 or sp^3d^2 type respectively, with orbital moments completely quenched. But the observed magnetic moment for the simple Ni^{++} ion varies from 3.2–3.44 Bohr. This is obviously due to a small contribution from the partially frozen orbital moments. This quenching effect is likely to be greater in octahedral d^2sp^3 penetration complexes with their stronger bonds. Besides, the electrons responsible for the magnetic moment in their case, being promoted to the outermost level, are fully exposed to the influence of the field of the neighbouring ions whereby their orbital moments are more or less completely quenched. This is clear from the following scheme.

It appears from these considerations that the complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_2)_6]^{4-}$ approaches the character of octahedral d^2sp^3 complex of the penetration type.

The μ_n -value of the central bivalent copper atom in its triple nitrites has been found to lie between 1.83 and 1.86, which is distinctly lower than that of Cu^{++} ion in simple salts.

which lies about 2.0 Bohr due to incompletely quenched orbital moment of the single unpaired electron in Cu^{++} ion. The lower value in $[\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$ suggests that the complex possibly belongs to the associated type with the formation of octahedral sp^3d^2 bonds as shown below.

The magnetic moment for the bivalent iron atom in its triple nitrite has been found to be 0.9 Bohr as against $5.3 \mu_B$ for Fe^{++} in simple iron salts. This abnormal reduction in the moment value is a strong evidence in favour of the formation of an octahedral penetration complex with d^2sp^3 hybrid bonds. Strictly speaking the moment should have been zero as shown in the following electronic configuration. The small paramagnetic moment observed is possibly due to the slight decomposition of the compound which is difficult to avoid. A similar value of $1 \mu_B$ has also been reported by Cambi, Ferrari and Colla (*Gazzetta*, 1936, 65, 1162).

The magnetic moment of hydrated and anhydrous nickel cyanides has been determined by various workers. The results are given below in a tabular form.

$\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2, 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Bose, <i>Nature</i> , 1930, 125, 708)	.. 3.0 Bohr approx.
$\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Cambi, <i>Gazzetta</i> , 1934, 64, 758)	.. 2.38 Bohr
$\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Cambi, <i>loc. cit.</i>)	.. 2.28 Bohr
$\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2$ (Fereday, <i>Proc. Phys. Soc.</i> , 1934, 46, 214)	.. 2.46 Bohr
$\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2$ (Cambi, <i>loc. cit.</i>)	.. 1.0 Bohr
$\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2$ (Fereday, <i>loc. cit.</i>)	.. 0.96 Bohr
$\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2$ (Bose, <i>loc. cit.</i>)	.. Practically diamagnetic
$\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2$ (Seres, <i>Annal. Physik</i> , (10) 1933, 20, 441)	.. 1.2 Bohr

The values obtained in the present investigation are :—

$\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2, 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2.2 Bohr ; $\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2.28 Bohr ; $\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2$, 0.65 Bohr.

It is seen that the value for $\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ agrees closely with that given by Cambi. The somewhat lower value for the trihydrate is rather unusual, if the possibilities of errors

planar square complex with dsp^2 bonds, $[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_4]^-$ with imperfectly quenched orbital moments as well as in the form of either a simple ion or a tetrahedral or ionic complex. Assuming a moment value of 2.6 Bohr for the square complex with dsp^2 bonds, the proportion of the bivalent cobalt atom in this form in the hydrated and the anhydrous cyanide may be shown to be about 55% in the former and 70% in the latter. Hence a structure similar to that suggested for nickel cyanide might also be assigned to the anhydrous cobaltous cyanide with a slightly lower degree of polymerisation.

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